

Hybrid Ensemble Learning Models for Detecting DNS Spoofing and Cache Poisoning Attacks

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Abstract—The Domain Name System (DNS) plays a critical role in Internet communication by translating human readable domain names into IP addresses. However, its open and distributed design makes it highly vulnerable to threats such as DNS spoofing and cache poisoning, which can redirect legitimate traffic to malicious destinations, enabling phishing, data theft, and malware distribution. Traditional rule-based intrusion detection systems (IDS) often fail to detect such evolving and zero-day attacks. This paper presents a hybrid stacking ensemble model for early detection of DNS spoofing and cache poisoning. The proposed framework integrates XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM as base learners, with a probability-calibrated Logistic Regression meta-classifier for optimal decision-making. A two-phase preprocessing pipeline is employed Isolation Forest-based anomaly filtering followed by SMOTE oversampling to address class imbalance. SHAP based feature importance analysis ensures transparency and interpretability. The model was evaluated on two datasets a real-world DNS exfiltration dataset containing 674K samples and a balanced simulated DNS attack dataset. Results demonstrate superior performance, achieving 99.81% accuracy (F1-score 99.69%) on the real-world dataset and 98.04% accuracy (F1-score 93.18%) on the simulated dataset, outperforming all baseline models. The proposed approach offers a robust, interpretable, and deployable solution for real-time DNS threat detection.

Index Terms—DNS Spoofing, DNS Cache Poisoning, Hybrid Ensemble Learning, Ensemble Model, Anomaly Detection, DNS Attack.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Domain Name System (DNS) is a core element of the Internet, translating human-readable domain names into IP addresses [1]. This essential service supports nearly all online activities, including web browsing, email, and IoT communications. However, due to its open and distributed architecture, DNS is vulnerable to multiple cyberattacks, particularly *DNS spoofing* and *cache poisoning*, which directly compromise the integrity of the resolution process.

In DNS spoofing, an attacker intercepts a query and responds with forged DNS records before the legitimate server can reply [2], often redirecting users to malicious domains for phishing or malware delivery. Cache poisoning is more persistent, inserting fraudulent entries into a resolver’s cache, which then serves incorrect responses to all future queries [3]. These attacks can remain undetected for long periods and impact large numbers of users [4]. Traditional defenses, such as signature-based intrusion detection systems (IDS), are often ineffective against zero-day or polymorphic attacks [5]. This

has driven interest in *machine learning* (ML)-based detection, which can identify complex patterns and anomalies in traffic without relying solely on predefined signatures [6]. However, many existing ML approaches rely on single classifiers, which may overfit or fail to generalize to evolving attack strategies [7]. Furthermore, the scarcity of high-quality, labeled DNS attack datasets limits the development and evaluation of robust detection models [8].

To address these challenges, we propose *DNSStack*, a hybrid ensemble-based detection framework designed to accurately detect DNS spoofing and cache poisoning attacks in both simulated and real-world scenarios. The system integrates XGBoost [9], CatBoost [10], and LightGBM [11] within a stacking ensemble, using a calibrated logistic regression meta-classifier for final prediction. A two-phase preprocessing pipeline applies Isolation Forest [12] for anomaly filtering and SMOTE [13] for class balancing, while SHAP based interpretability [14] provides transparent insights into model decisions.

The main contributions of this work are:

- **Comprehensive Data Pipeline:** Created a combined dataset from a real-world exfiltration dataset [8] and a custom-simulated DNS attack dataset to ensure diverse coverage.
- **Feature Engineering:** Selected highly discriminative features such as TTL anomalies, domain entropy, and transaction ID mismatches using statistical tests and feature importance scores.
- **Hybrid Ensemble Model:** Designed a stacking model with XGBoost [9], LightGBM [11], and CatBoost [10] as base learners, and calibrated logistic regression as the meta-classifier.
- **Imbalance and Noise Handling:** Applied Isolation Forest [12] for outlier removal and SMOTE [13] for synthetic oversampling to improve minority class detection.
- **Performance and Transparency:** Achieved 98.04% accuracy and a macro F1-score of 0.9318, with SHAP analysis [14] for model explainability.

II. RELATED WORK

Detection of DNS spoofing and cache poisoning attacks has evolved significantly, moving from static heuristic-based methods to more adaptive machine learning and hybrid techniques. Early approaches primarily relied on fixed indicators such as

anomalous transaction IDs, irregular TTL values, or unusual query rates [1], [4]. While these methods were effective against basic attacks, they were often circumvented by adversaries capable of mimicking legitimate DNS behaviors.

Mahdavi et al. [15] proposed a hybrid lightweight machine learning framework that integrates both stateless and stateful DNS traffic features to detect high- and low-rate data exfiltration. Utilizing a Random Forest classifier, their method achieved an accuracy of 97.97% and demonstrated robustness against subtle attacks. However, it depended on fixed detection thresholds, required well-labeled datasets, and lacked validation in real-world network scenarios.

Parineeta and Dash [16] introduced hybrid deep learning architectures combining Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), as well as Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) and CNN, for DNS spoofing detection in financial environments. Their LSTM CNN model achieved an accuracy of 99.7% by jointly capturing temporal and spatial patterns in DNS traffic. Despite the high performance, these models demand substantial computational resources and frequent retraining, which challenge scalability for large-scale, real-time deployment.

Hussain et al. [17] tackled spoofing and cache poisoning by employing RSA-based encryption on DNS queries and responses to secure transaction IDs and IP addresses. This approach effectively blocked forged replies with minimal delay but faced practical issues related to key management, scalability, and resilience against advanced or blended attack techniques.

Dutta et al. [18] combined hybrid machine learning classifiers with SHAP explainability [14] for DNS anomaly detection, achieving 96.1% accuracy while providing interpretable feature importance insights for analysts. Although the enhanced interpretability improved trust in automated decisions, the SHAP computations introduced latency, and the approach was not evaluated against adversarial traffic.

While these studies have made significant strides, they share common limitations, including overreliance on static or synthetic datasets, limited adaptability to evolving attack strategies, and trade-offs among accuracy, efficiency, and interpretability [6], [7]. To address these gaps, our work proposes an integrated pipeline combining Isolation Forest-based anomaly filtering [12], SMOTE balancing [13], and a stacking ensemble of gradient boosting models (XGBoost [9], LightGBM [11], CatBoost [10]) with a calibrated Logistic Regression meta-classifier. This design achieves high accuracy and recall while maintaining transparency through SHAP analysis [14], ensuring effectiveness in both simulated and real-world DNS environments.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our proposed detection framework integrates rigorous pre-processing, advanced feature engineering, and a hybrid stacking ensemble to accurately identify DNS spoofing and cache poisoning attacks. The process begins with acquiring high-quality datasets from both real-world and simulated sources,

followed by systematic cleaning, transformation, and balancing steps. The prepared data then passes through an anomaly filtering stage before training a multi-model ensemble, whose predictions are later interpreted using explainable AI techniques. This workflow ensures both high performance and transparency in decision-making.

An overview of the complete methodology is presented in Fig. 1, outlining each stage from data acquisition to final model interpretation.

Fig. 1. Proposed methodology pipeline for DNS attack detection.

A. Datasets

To ensure robustness across diverse traffic patterns, we used two complementary datasets: a real-world exfiltration dataset and a custom-generated simulated DNS attack dataset.

1) *Real-World Exfiltration Dataset*: The first dataset was obtained from Mendeley Data [8], containing approximately 674,000 DNS records (74% benign, 26% malicious). Duplicate entries were removed, reducing the dataset to 587,000 clean samples. Since no missing values or major outliers were present, minimal cleaning was required. Less informative features were dropped, retaining ten critical attributes such as entropy, subdomain_count, and digit_ratio. Severe class imbalance was addressed using SMOTE [13], resulting in an equal distribution of 309,000 samples per class. A larger validation set of 1.2M entries (five attack types, 23 features) was later used to assess real-world performance.

2) *Simulated DNS Attack Dataset*: The second dataset was generated using Scapy [19] for traffic generation and

Tshark [20] for packet analysis, inspired by the CIC-IDS2017 dataset [21]. It contains three balanced classes benign, spoofing, and cache poisoning each representing 33.33% of 500,000 total records. Key engineered features included `ttl_log`, `txid_mismatch`, `subdomain_count`, and `port_diff`. Outliers in numerical fields were capped using IQR-based thresholds. After feature importance analysis, 15 highly discriminative attributes were retained. The dataset was split into 400,000 training and 100,000 testing samples, maintaining balanced class proportions.

B. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing was a multi-stage pipeline ensuring consistency, quality, and relevance of the training data. The workflow, shown in Fig. 2, consisted of:

- 1) **Loading & Inspection:** Initial dataset import and structure verification.
- 2) **Cleaning:** Duplicate removal, median/mode imputation for rare missing values, and outlier capping via IQR.
- 3) **Feature Engineering:** Creation of behavioral and statistical indicators from raw DNS packet fields.
- 4) **Feature Selection:** Combined ranking from F-test, Mutual Information, and Random Forest importance scores.
- 5) **Balancing:** SMOTE oversampling applied to the minority class [13].
- 6) **Normalization:** StandardScaler (Z-score normalization) applied to align feature ranges.

Fig. 2. Data preprocessing workflow.

C. Modeling Approach

Our detection framework adopts a two-stage strategy:

- **Anomaly Filtering:** An Isolation Forest algorithm [12] removes abnormal or noisy instances prior to training, reducing the risk of overfitting.
- **Stacking Ensemble:** Three state-of-the-art gradient boosting models XGBoost [9], LightGBM [11], and CatBoost [10] serve as base learners. Their probability outputs are combined using a calibrated Logistic Regression meta-classifier [22], [23], which improves generalization and stability.

D. Evaluation and Explainability

The trained model is evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and Macro F1-score, with class-level performance illustrated via a Confusion Matrix. SHAP analysis [14] is employed to quantify feature contributions and provide transparency in model predictions.

Feature importance visualizations for both datasets are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, highlighting the most influential predictors.

Fig. 3. Top-ranked features from the real-world exfiltration dataset.

Fig. 4. Top-ranked features from the simulated DNS dataset.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This section presents the experimental setup, evaluation metrics, and empirical results obtained from both datasets: the Real-World Exfiltration dataset [8] and the Simulated DNS Spoofing and Cache Poisoning dataset. Our aim is to evaluate

the effectiveness of the proposed hybrid ensemble against strong baseline learners, as well as to compare with related state-of-the-art approaches.

A. Experimental Setup

All experiments were conducted on a high-performance workstation equipped with an Intel Core i7-10700K CPU, 32 GB RAM, and Windows 11 OS. Python 3.10 was used with Scikit-learn 1.3, XGBoost [9] 1.7, CatBoost [10] 1.2, and LightGBM [11] 3.3. To ensure robust evaluation, we adopted stratified 5-fold cross-validation, preserving the original class distribution in each fold. Hyperparameters for all models were optimized using an exhaustive grid search over key parameters such as learning rate, max depth, and regularization terms.

B. Evaluation Metrics

Performance was assessed using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and Macro F1-score. Macro-averaging was selected to treat all classes equally, preventing dominance by the majority class in imbalanced settings [13]. Given the security-critical nature of this task, Recall was considered particularly important to minimize false negatives, while F1-score provided a balanced view of Precision–Recall trade-offs.

C. Performance on the Real-World Exfiltration Dataset

Table I reports the results for the real-world dataset. The proposed meta-ensemble achieved the highest accuracy (**99.81%**) and Macro F1-score (**99.69%**), marginally outperforming all base learners. This indicates that the ensemble strategy successfully leverages complementary strengths of individual models.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE METRICS ON THE EXFILTRATION DATASET

Algorithm	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1
XGBoost	99.75	99.72	99.74	99.72
CatBoost	99.76	99.67	99.74	99.61
LightGBM	99.75	99.61	99.74	99.55
Meta-Ensemble	99.81	99.74	99.80	99.69

The confusion matrix in Fig. 5 demonstrates near-perfect classification for both benign and malicious traffic, with negligible false positives and false negatives.

D. Performance on the Simulated Dataset

For the simulated dataset, results are presented in Table II. The meta-ensemble achieved **98.04%** accuracy and a Macro F1-score of **93.18%**, outperforming all baselines and demonstrating strong generalization even on synthetic traffic patterns.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS ON THE SIMULATED DATASET

Algorithm	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1
XGBoost	97.45	86.00	96.75	90.45
CatBoost	97.98	89.17	95.64	91.89
LightGBM	97.62	88.18	98.24	92.22
Meta-Ensemble	98.04	89.74	97.97	93.18

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix for the Exfiltration Dataset.

The confusion matrix in Fig. 6 shows consistent detection capability across benign, spoofing, and cache poisoning classes, with high recall for minority attack categories.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix for the Simulated Dataset.

E. ROC Curve Analysis

The ROC curves in Figs. 7 and 8 exhibit micro-average AUC values exceeding 0.999 for both datasets, confirming exceptional discriminative performance. The close-to-ideal curve shapes indicate that the models are robust to threshold variations, a desirable property for real-time intrusion detection systems.

F. Comparative Performance with Existing Studies

Table III compares our model against prior works on DNS anomaly detection, including Mahdavi et al. [15], Parineeta and Dash [16], Hussain et al. [17], and Dutta et al. [18]. The proposed hybrid ensemble not only achieves the highest accuracy but also maintains strong recall, highlighting its

Fig. 7. ROC curves for the Exfiltration Dataset.

Fig. 8. ROC curves for the Simulated Dataset.

effectiveness in detecting both frequent and rare attack patterns. This improvement can be attributed to the combination of diverse gradient boosting algorithms, strategic anomaly filtering [12], and class balancing techniques [13].

V. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid stacking ensemble consistently outperforms individual base models on both datasets. The integration of Isolation Forest [12] with gradient boosting learners (XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM) and a calibrated Logistic Regression meta-learner significantly improved the detection of minority attack classes, yielding higher Macro F1-scores and recall. Moreover, AUC values above 0.999 confirm excellent discriminative capability across thresholds. The preprocessing pipeline comprising SMOTE balancing [13], feature selection, and normalization played a crucial role in ensuring stable and generalizable performance. Compared to related works [15]–[18], the model achieved higher accuracy without sacrificing interpretability, as verified through SHAP analysis [14]. Despite these strong results, the approach introduces additional computational overhead, and the simulated dataset may not fully capture the complexity of real-world traffic. Future work will focus on latency reduction and validation on larger, heterogeneous datasets.

A. Model Interpretability with SHAP

The SHAP analysis [14] in Fig. 9 reveals that features such as *src_ip_int*, *dns_id_int*, and *ttl_log* have the most substantial influence on classification outcomes. This enhances model transparency and provides actionable insights for proactive DNS security monitoring, enabling administrators to trace and understand high-impact feature behaviors.

Fig. 9. Mean absolute SHAP values showing feature importance for each class.

B. Strengths and Limitations

Key strengths of the proposed approach include:

- Achieving exceptional accuracy and recall on both real-world and simulated datasets.
- Effectively addressing severe class imbalance.
- Offering interpretable decision-making through SHAP-based analysis [14].

The main limitations are the partial reliance on simulated data for certain attack types and increased training costs due to the ensemble’s complexity. Future research will investigate optimizations for real-time deployment, scalability, and cross-environment robustness.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a hybrid stacking ensemble framework that integrates Isolation Forest for anomaly filtering with gradient boosting learners (XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM) and a calibrated Logistic Regression meta-learner for the detection of DNS spoofing, cache poisoning, and data exfiltration attacks. The proposed approach consistently outperformed individual base models, achieving superior accuracy, recall, and macro-averaged F1-scores on both real-world and simulated datasets. Preprocessing steps such as feature selection, class balancing via SMOTE, and normalization contributed significantly to the robustness and generalization capability of the model. The results highlight the framework’s potential for deployment in

TABLE III
COMPARISON OF RELATED WORKS AND PROPOSED MODEL

Ref.	Dataset	Attack Type	Models	Accuracy (%)
[15]	DNSExfiltrator dataset simulated	Data Exfiltration	Random Forest, MLP, SVM	97.97
[16]	Real-world financial traffic	DNS Spoofing	LSTM, CNN, GRU-CNN	96.4
[17]	Simulated DNS traffic	Spoofing & Cache Poisoning	RSA-based protection	Successful prevention
[18]	130k+ legitimate/DGA domains	Typo-squatting	Bagging Ensemble	87.7
Our Model	Exfiltration	Data Exfiltration, Spoofing, Cache Poisoning	Isolation Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, Logistic Regression	99.81
	Simulated			98.04

high-throughput DNS monitoring environments, with micro-average AUC values exceeding 0.999 across datasets. While the method introduces some computational overhead and simulated traffic may not capture all nuances of real-world conditions, its high interpretability validated through SHAP analysis [14] makes it suitable for security operations where explainability is critical.

Future research directions include extending the methodology to DNS-over-HTTPS (DoH) traffic, integrating temporal deep learning models (such as LSTM, Transformer-based architectures) for sequence-aware detection, and conducting large-scale, real-time deployment trials in production networks. These enhancements will focus on improving scalability, reducing inference latency, and expanding applicability to broader network security scenarios.

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